

STUDY OF RESISTANCE OF *ESCHERICHIA COLI* IN ISOTONIC SOLUTION IN PREPARATION FOR IMMOBILIZATION ON SOLID ALUMINUM OXIDE CARRIERS

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Abstract. *The paper provides data on studying the persorption properties and salt tolerance of growing cells of the bacterium Escherichia coli for immobilization on certain types of composite microplasma coating of aluminum oxide. It was revealed that after keeping the Escherichia coli culture in an isotonic solution (NaCl) for 1 hour 35 minutes, 84.2% of stable vegetative cells intended for sorption were found. It has been established that the stability of the Escherichia coli culture is maintained between time intervals of 1:00 and 1:30 hours.*

Keywords: *escherichia coli, bacteria, cultivation, isotonic solution, exposure time, cell counting, stability, preparation for immobilization.*

Introduction

Escherichia coli is a species of Gram-negative rod-shaped bacteria that are common in the lower intestine of warm-blooded animals. Most strains of *E. coli* are harmless, but some strains can cause severe food poisoning. Non-pathogenic *E. coli* bacteria, which normally inhabit the intestine in large quantities, can nevertheless cause pathology when they enter other organs or cavities of the human body. Bacteria can be easily grown in the laboratory, so *E. coli* plays an important role in genetic research [1-3]. *E. coli* is one of the most studied prokaryotic microorganisms and one of the most important model objects of biotechnology and microbiology. *E. coli* cells immobilized by physical absorption or cross-linking have the advantage of low cost, but they usually have low recovery of activity and poor suitability for reuse. An improved approach is cross-linking after adsorption or aggregation of the cells of this bacterium [4].

It is known that immobilized microbial cells are widely used in various fields of biotechnology, such as phenol degradation [5], ethanol production [6], and biosensors [7]. Cell immobilization methods include non-specific adsorption, covalent attachment, and entrapment. Immobilization by non-specific adsorption may require long incubation times (up to 12 h) and is sensitive to changes in pH, temperature, and ionic strength. All of these factors can lead to cell removal from the surface [8]. Covalent attachment is often achieved by activating a surface with a cross-linking agent such as glutaraldehyde and then attaching the cell via surface amino groups [9]. Cells can also be immobilized by forming coordination bonds with metal-activated carriers.

Gregory and others describe a method for immobilizing *Escherichia coli* cells on microtiter plate well surfaces using the antimicrobial peptide cecropin P1. *E. coli* K-12 cells were immobilized in the pH range from 5 to 10, and the *E. coli* O157:H7 strain was immobilized more

effectively at pH from 5 to 8. The peptide could not bind to the cells at ionic strengths greater than 0.5 M [10].

The development of practical methods that include a biological element as a component depends on the ability to stabilize or preserve this biological element, be it a large molecule or a particle.

In recent years, the range of methods for preserving the activity of biological objects has expanded significantly, and immobilization plays an increasingly important role in the development of these methods. Immobilization is the process of fixing a biological object using physicochemical forces on various carriers, taking into account their structure and properties.

For effective immobilization of microorganism cells, in particular bacteria, it is necessary to use filtered homogeneously grown *Escherichia coli* cells in a weak isotonic saline solution for an accurate count of their cells intended for immobilization and, accordingly, after immobilization.

The aim of the work is to determine the viability of vegetative cells of a non-pathogenic strain of *Escherichia coli* in an isotonic solution (0.9%, NaCl) and the stability time of cells filtered through a membrane filter (0.47 μm), intended for further immobilization on solid aluminum oxide carriers.

Materials and methods of the study

The bacterial incubation procedures were carried out at room temperature with gentle shaking on shakers with a rotation speed of 50 rpm. The concentrations of viable cells in the cultures were determined by diluting the cultures with their subsequent seeding on Petri dishes with agar and counting the number of colonies obtained.

For this purpose, overnight cultures of the non-pathogenic *E. coli* strain were grown in liquid MPB medium (Hi-media) at 37 ° C with shaking. Serial dilutions of cell cultures were prepared in physiological solution. Dilutions were added to the wells of the plate in aliquots of 200 μl . Four repetitions of each dilution were used.

Results and their discussion

Immobilization systems can be divided into completely artificial and natural origin. In the first category, microbial (or eukaryotic) cells are artificially captured or attached to various matrices, where they retain or do not retain a viable state depending on the degree of harmfulness and inefficiency of the immobilization procedure.

The nutrient medium plays an important role both in growth and in the immobilization process, since it can affect the immobilization process and productivity of cells, affecting their long-term growth. Therefore, we propose a technique for using cell cultures separated from the culture medium using a membrane filter and further washing the bacterial cell sediment with a sodium chloride solution.

For this purpose, a membrane filter connected to an air blowing pump was added to sterile laboratory flasks with 100 ml of isotonic NaCl solution at a concentration of 0.9%. After shaking the membrane filter and washing the cells from the filter, the number of *E. coli* ATCC 25922 cells (CFU / ml) in the isotonic solution was counted. In this isotonic solution, the number of cells was 7.8 million cells. The degree of cell exposure was monitored every 10-15-20 minutes by counting colony forming units (CFU) in an isotonic NaCl solution, as well as under a microscope using a Goryaev chamber (Table 1). As can be seen from Table 1, after exposure of the *Escherichia coli* culture in an isotonic solution for 1 hour 35 minutes, 84.2% of live vegetative cells were detected.

It should be noted that this method allows you to observe live microorganisms, make a quantitative analysis indicating the number of microorganisms per unit volume (CFU/ml) of the culture medium.

Table 1

Stability of Escherichia coli cells in an isotonic solution depending on exposure at room temperatures (24 °C).

Initial concentration of Escherichia coli cells grown on a special selective medium with peptone and passed through a membrane filter								
Total number of cells, million/piece	950 000	900 000	812 500	775 000	750 000	800 000	575 000	437 500
Sustaining Escherichia coli cells on a 0.9% NaCl solution depending on time								
Incubation hours	0,0	0,16	0,5	0,45	1 h 15	1 h 35	1 h 55	2 h 13
Number of stable Escherichia coli cells, sustained in a 0.9% NaCl solution								
%, live cells after washing	100	94,7368	85,526	81,5789	78,947	84,2105	60,526	46,05

The initial titer after membrane filtration is 1,406,250,000 million/ml. Next, the stability of E. coli bacterial cells on isotonic solution was studied before preparation for immobilization on sorbents (Table 2). As can be seen from Table 2, the stability of the Escherichia coli culture is maintained between 1:30 hour intervals.

Table 2

Stability of bacterial cells on isotonic Escherichia coli before preparation for immobilization on solid sorbents

Minutes		16	30	45	1 hour15 min	1,5 hour5 min	1 hour55 min	2 hour13 min
Avg. number of cells, million/pcs	950 000	900 000	812 500	775 000	750 000	800 000	575 000	437 500
Minutes/hours of incubation	0,0/0,0	16/0,16	30/0,5	45/0,45	75/1 h 15	95/1 h 35	115/1 h 55	133/2 h 13
% living cells	100	94,7368	85,526	81,5789	78,947	84,2105	60,526	46,05

It is known that spontaneous adsorption of microbial cells on various types of carriers provides natural immobilization systems, in which the cells are attached to their substrate by weak (non-covalent), usually non-specific interactions such as electrostatic, ionic interactions. Under suitable environmental conditions, this initial adsorption step can be followed by colonization of the carrier by microorganisms, resulting in the formation of a biofilm in which the microorganisms are embedded in a matrix of extracellular polymers that they themselves secrete.

Due to the presence of this polymer paste, biofilms are more firmly attached to their substrate than simply adsorbed cells. In the future, in addition to practical applications, the study of embedded or encapsulated cells and/or enzymes, proteins will contribute to a better understanding of their functioning under in vivo conditions.

The next stage of research is ongoing on the immobilization of stable *Escherichia coli* cells on functionally active new generation sorbents formed by microarc oxidation of aluminum metal oxide composite coatings, by targeted optimization of the composition and structure for the immobilization of microorganism cells.

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